

Coordination Behaviour of Chloroquine towards some Biologically Significant Metal Ions

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The complexing behaviour of one of the most important and widely used antimalarial drugs, chloroquine [7-chloro-4-(4-diethylamino-1-methylbutylamino)quinoline], with essential elements of the first transition series has not been studied, although, its interaction with metal ions in the gut

has been implicated¹ after its oral intake. In continuation of our earlier work on complexing behaviour of antimalarial drugs², we report herein the synthesis and properties of chloroquine complexes with biologically essential first row transition metal ions.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) were coloured and exhibited paramagnetic behaviour. Molar conductance values ($4-10 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) of all the complexes indicated their non-electrolytic nature. The complexes were found soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide and except cobalt(II) complex (2), all other complexes were insoluble in water. Microanalytical data indicated the incorporation of one molecule of chloroquine in the coordination sphere. The data further indicated that other ligands, namely, one water molecule, one oxygen and one sulphate ion in oxovanadium(IV) complex (1) or one water molecule and two chloride ions in other complexes (2-4) were also coordinated with the central metal ion. The thermal stability of the complexes upto 200° suggested the absence of lattice water in these complexes³. The complexes may, therefore, be represented by the general formula $[\text{VOL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{SO}_4]$ (1) or $[\text{ML}(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}_2]$ (L=chloroquine, M=Co, Ni or Cu; 2-4). The detailed structures of the complexes were derived from their magnetic moments, infrared and electronic spectral studies.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	Mol. formula/ (colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
		C	H	N	Cl	Metal
1	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_5\text{SV}^a$ (Dark green)	41.66 (43.15)	5.62 (5.59)	8.43 (8.39)	7.00 (7.09)	10.20 (10.18)
2	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{Cl}_2\text{CoN}_3\text{O}$ (Blue)	45.99 (46.20)	5.92 (5.98)	8.93 (8.98)	22.51 (22.78)	12.20 (12.62)
3	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{Cl}_3\text{NiN}_3\text{O}$ (Apple green)	46.10 (46.23)	5.89 (5.99)	8.90 (8.98)	22.13 (22.79)	12.45 (12.56)
4	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{Cl}_2\text{CuN}_3\text{O}$ (Dirty green)	46.01 (45.76)	5.99 (5.93)	8.80 (8.89)	22.12 (22.56)	13.05 (13.45)

^aAnalysis S : Found 6.25, Calcd. 6.39%.

The infrared spectral assignments for chloroquine and its complexes are detailed in Table 2. A decrease in frequency of NH stretching in the spectra of the chloroquine complexes indicated that the secondary nitrogen of chloroquine participated in coordination. The new bands appearing at $3600-3500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 1630 cm^{-1} in the complexes may be attributed to OH stretching and bending vibrations of coordinated water³. The alterations in the position of aromatic skeletal stretching vibrations on complexation indicated the involvement of ring nitrogen of chloroquine in coordination. The absorption due to C—N (side-chain tertiary nitrogen of chloroquine) also suffered slight shifting indicating that chloroquine is also coordinated to the central metal ion through this nitrogen. A very sharp band at 976 cm^{-1} in the oxovanadium(IV) complex was assigned to V=O stretching vibration. The appearance of three strong bands at 1000 , 1070 and 1120 cm^{-1} in the oxovanadium(IV) complex for the sulphato group indicated its unidentate mode of coordination⁴. The new bands observed at $600-400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA (cm^{-1}) OF CHLOROQUINE AND ITS COMPLEXES (1-4)

Chloroquine	1	2	3	4	Assignments
—	3 448	3 552	3 585	3 520	ν_{OH} coordinated water
3 420	3 390	3 256	3 275	3 252	ν_{NH}
—	1 630	1 632	1 630	1 630	δ_{OH} coordinated water
1 610	1 616	1 620	1 611	1 620	Aromatic skeletal absorption
1 580	1 580	1 590	1 580	1 582	
1 538	1 535	1 535	1 530	1 525	
1 464	1 460	1 464	1 460	1 460	
1 356	1 350	1 350	1 370	1 350	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ tertiary
1 260	1 250	1 250	1 275	1 270	
1 150	1 145	1 148	1 158	1 156	
—	1 120	—	—	—	Unidentate sulphato group
—	1 070	—	—	—	
—	1 000	—	—	—	
—	976	—	—	—	$\nu_{\text{V=O}}$
672	640	660	670	665	$\nu_{\text{C-Cl}}$
—	620	620	570	650	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$
—	—	492	410	450	$\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$

were assigned to M—N and M—Cl stretching vibrations. The studies indicated that chloroquine behaved as a tridentate ligand, the coordination being via all the three nitrogens.

The room temperature magnetic moment values of 5.10, 3.10 and 1.81 B.M. for cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes indicated $^4T_{1g}$, $^3A_{2g}$ and 2E_g ground states respectively for octahedral metal ions⁵. The electronic spectra which displayed bands at 8500 [$^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(F)$] (ν_1), 17200 [$^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}(F)$] (ν_2) and 21200 cm^{-1} [$^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$] (ν_3) for the cobalt(II) complex, at 9700 [$^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}(F)$] (ν_1), 16100 [$^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(F)$] (ν_2) and 24100 cm^{-1} [$^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$] (ν_3) for the nickel(II) complex and a broad band at $14500-15000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [$^2E_g \rightarrow ^2T_{2g}$] for the copper(II) complex, corroborated octahedral geometry for these complexes. The electronic spectrum of oxovanadium(IV) complex exhibiting two bands at 17000 ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{yz}$, d_{xz}) (ν_1) and 23000 cm^{-1} ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) (ν_2) in combination with a magnetic moment value of 1.71 B.M., was also consistent with the octahedral geometry around the metal ion. However, in view of the fact that water, sulphate and chloride ions are weaker ligands² than chloroquine, the complexes have been assigned tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry.

Experimental

Chloroquine (free base) was obtained by treating its diphosphate salt (Sigma) with aqueous sodium carbonate. The metal salts and solvents used were of analytical grade.

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents of the complexes were estimated on a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyser whereas chlorine and sulphur were estimated gravimetrically⁶. The metals, except vanadium, were estimated on a Varian Techtron atomic absorption spectrometer AA-120. Vanadium was estimated gravimetrically⁶. The infrared

and electronic spectra were recorded on Hitachi 270-50 and Cecil spectrophotometers respectively. Molecular weights were determined on a Beckmann freezing point apparatus. Magnetic moment measurement was made by Gouy's method using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as calibrant. Molar conductance was determined in dimethyl sulphoxide using $10^{-6}M$ solution of the complex.

Metal complexes: Sulphatmonoquo-7-chloro-4-(4-diethylamino-1-methylbutylamine)quinolineoxovanadium(IV) (1), dichloromonoquo-7-chloro-4-(4-diethylamino-1-methylbutylamino)quinolinecobalt(II)/nickel(II)/copper(II) (2-4 respectively) complexes were prepared by refluxing equimolar solution of chloroquine in ethanol with aqueous solution of vanadyl sulphate or ethanolic solution of cobalt(II) or nickel(II) or copper(II) chloride for 3, 5, 12 or 0.5 h respectively. The reaction mixture was concentrated and allowed to stand overnight. The crystallised complexes were washed successively with water, alcohol and ether and dried under reduced pressure (yield ~70%).

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